

Editorial citing behaviour in American Economic Review

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Introduction

In this study we explore whether authors cite members of the editorial board of the journals they are targeting as a strategy to be published. We focus on *American Economic Review*, one of the top journals in economics, for its relevance in obtaining tenure and career progression (Heckman and Moktan, 2020). We show that citing a member of the editorial board is a prevalent behaviour among academics. This is not surprising considering that members of the editorial board are well renowned academics within their field. Nevertheless, we are able to observe the adjustments happening during the publishing process, by comparing the references between the latest working paper version and the published version of the article. We take all articles published in *American Economic Review* between the years 2005 and 2010. We find that there is a higher proportion of members of the editorial board in the published version, compared to the working paper version. When exploring what predicts a higher likelihood of adding references of the editorial board, we find that authors with a lower academic age (measured as the time between PhD conferral and article publication) are more likely to cite additional members of the editorial board. There is also a positive relation between the time that it takes a working paper to be published and the total number of authors.

Prevalence of Editorial Citations

We first want to establish how many published papers cite a member of the editorial board. We collect the names of all editors, co-editors and members of the editorial board for the top 5 journals in economics (including *American Economic Review*) by looking at the first available issue of each year that contained the names between 1970 and 2018. We obtained the full-text articles from JSTOR and the reference lists from SCOPUS. We then matched the authors and editors using their surname and first letter of their given name. From a sample of 8072 papers, 663 cite the editor, 1916 cite at least one co-editor, 3380 cite at least one associate editor and 4019 (roughly 50%) cite any member of the editorial board.

Dataset American Economic Review

We collect a total of 374 articles published in the journal *American Economic Review* between the

years 2005 and 2010. We then search for available working paper versions of the article. We find 313 working paper articles that uniquely match to the published version. We then do a manual check of the reference list for both the working paper and the published version. With this information, we create a dummy variable for journal articles that referenced a member of the editorial board at least once more than they did in the working paper version.

In addition, we collect biographical background information for the authors of 308 out of the 313 papers analysed. We look at academic age, as it is possible that early career researchers are particularly incentivised to publish in a top journal to advance in their careers, thus we hypothesize that academic age is negatively related to the likelihood of adding a reference. We also look at the ranking of the authors' affiliation. Here we use the ranking developed by Amir and Knauff (2008), which ranks economics departments from 1 to 58. For any university outside this ranking we code it with the value 59. Another interesting variable is the time it takes from working paper to published version. Here one could expect that the longer it takes to publish a paper, the higher the probability that the authors would consider adding an additional reference of an editorial member in order to increase the likelihood of getting published. We also control for gender, length of paper and total number of references per paper. For papers with multiple authors, we calculate academic age, gender and university ranking as an average.

Results and Discussion

Overall within the sample, 145 out of 313 papers cite a member of the editorial board in the published version, that has not been already cited in the working paper. In addition, 52 out of 313 (16.51%) published papers cite at least an additional reference of an editorial board member, compared to the reference list of the working paper.

Table 1. Probit regressions for an additional editorial reference. Standard errors (robust) in parentheses. Marginal effects are in italics.

	Editorial reference added	Editorial reference added
Academic age	-0.0240*	-0.0259*

	(0.0102)	(0.0105)
	-0.00572	-0.00604
Uni ranking	0.00245	0.00110
	(0.00446)	(0.00455)
	0.000584	0.000256
Wp to publication	0.118*	0.0964†
	(0.0549)	(0.0579)
	0.0282	0.0224
female	-0.203	-0.178
	(0.318)	(0.318)
	-0.0485	-0.0415
# of authors	0.212†	0.209†
	(0.115)	(0.115)
	0.0505	0.0486
Tot # references		-0.000100
		(0.00506)
		-0.0000233
# pages		0.000281
		(0.0133)
		0.0000655
Constant	-1.497***	-1.711***
	(0.336)	(0.485)
Year fixed-effects	No	Yes
Observations	308	308
Pseudo R ²	0.040	0.062

We further explore the characteristics that predict adding an editorial reference. We conducted probit regression models with the independent variable being a binary of adding at least one additional editorial reference (see Table 1). The first model considers the influence of academic age, university ranking, time lapse between first working paper and publication, share of female authors and number of authors. The second model further controls for length of paper, number of references and year of publication.

Consistent with our expectations, academic age is negatively related to adding an editorial reference ($p=0.019$) and this effect remains significant after controlling for additional paper characteristics and year fixed-effects ($p=0.014$). In figure 1, we show the predicted effect of academic age on additional editorial citations. Less experienced economists are more likely to add an editorial reference in the published version, compared to those economists with 30 to 40 years of experience. The time lapse between working paper and publication shows a positive coefficient ($p=0.031$), supporting the hypothesis that authors are more likely to cite an editor if the paper takes longer to be published, but the results are only weakly significant once we control for paper characteristics ($p=0.096$). Lastly, there is also a positive relation between number of authors and adding an editorial reference ($p=0.069$).

Figure 1. Predicted effect of academic age on likelihood of adding a reference.

Overall there is a large proportion of authors of articles in top economics journals that cite a member of the editorial board. Many of these editorial citations are not introduced in the working paper version, but only once they are published in the targeted journal. A core question that remains is whether the authors cite a member of the editorial board as a strategy to get published or whether the editorial board influences this addition. Interestingly, early career economists, whose career is more dependent on publishing in a top journal, are the ones more likely to add an extra editorial reference. Nevertheless there are some limitations in this study. The sample size of the analysis is restricted to one single journal. It is also restricted to a few years, and it has been shown that journal article characteristics within the same journal change over time (Torgler and Piatti, 2013). A more fine-grained analysis can also establish whether citing behaviour changes among different subfields of economics as a result of the subfield size and maturity.

References and Citations

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